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Italiadomani
PIANO NAZIONALE
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SAPIENZA
UNIVERSITÀ DI ROMA
ALMA MATER STUDIORUM
UNIVERSITÀ DI BOLOGNA
UNIVERSITÀ
PERUGINA

Summary

1. INTRODUCTION.....	3
1. PROJECT MANAGEMENT AND ADMINISTRATION (WP1000).....	4
2. SYSTEM DEFINITION (WP2000).....	7
2.1. Systematic literature review.....	7
2.2.3 Literature review findings.....	9
2.2. Experimental plant details	10
2.3. STAMP model and STPA analysis.....	14
2.4. Draft resilience metrics.....	26
3. CYBER-PHYSICAL DIGITAL TWIN DEVELOPMENT (WP3000).....	27
3.1. Modelled plant components	28
3.1.1. Pump-ejector system.....	28
3.1.2. Closed vertical tank	28
3.1.3. PID regulators and system criticalities	29
3.2. Experimental campaign to model the DIGITAL TWIN	32
3.3. The plant DIGITAL TWIN and operator’s action	38
4. HUMAN DIGITAL TWIN DEVELOPMENT (WP4000).....	39
5. CRITICALITY ASSESSMENT OF HHIL DIGITAL TWIN (WP5000).....	44
5.1. Scenario 1 - Anomalous behavior of the vertical tank level	44
5.2. Scenario 2 – Anomalous behavior of the vertical tank pressure.....	45
5.3. Human digital twin integration.....	46
6. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE ACTIVITIES.....	47
ACKNOWLEDGEMENT.....	47

1. INTRODUCTION

This report describes the activities conducted during the first year of the Resilience Management to Industrial Systems Threats (RESIST) project. This project aims to develop a digital twin simulation environment for assessing the resilience of industrial socio-technical plants against cyber-attacks. The project objective is to develop a framework for simulating cyber-socio-technical systems (CSTS) functioning. Beyond the methodological development, the framework is being validated in a real-world plant offering recommendations for adapting the methodology to diverse industrial domains. The project advances the field of Systems Engineering and Resilience Engineering by combining different disciplines and contexts to produce a comprehensive analysis of current complex industrial systems with cyber components. The project is coordinated by Sapienza Department of Mechanical and Aerospace Engineering, and it involves the Department of Industrial Engineering, University of Bologna, and the Department of Industrial Engineering and Mathematical Science, University Politecnica delle Marche.

During the first year of the project, the research activities focused on a comprehensive definition of the system to be analyzed, and on the development of the plant digital twin and the human digital twin. **Table 1** summarizes the activities conducted (described in detail in the following paragraphs) with their respective work packages (WPs), and the corresponding responsible project's unit.

Table 1. Summary of the project's activities.

<i>WP</i>	<i>Activity</i>	<i>WP leader</i>	<i>Status</i>
WP1000	Project management and administration	Sapienza University of Rome	Ongoing
WP2000	System definition	Sapienza University of Rome	Completed
WP3000	Cyber-physical digital twin development	University Politecnica delle Marche	Ongoing
WP4000	Human digital twin development	University of Bologna	Ongoing
WP5000	Criticality assessment of human-hardware in the loop digital twin	University Politecnica delle Marche	To be started on November 1 st , 2024
WP6000	Analysis, exploitation, and dissemination of results	University of Bologna	To be started on April 1 st , 2024

Figure 1 shows the Gantt chart of the project. WP2000 was concluded during the first year of the project, while WP3000 and WP4000 are approaching conclusion. The activities conducted for WP3000 and WP4000 are in line with what was planned and will be completed in the following month, with no extension expected. During the second year of the project, WP5000 and WP6000 will be conducted. Project management and administration activities are being carried out according to the project Gantt and no variations were found compared to what was defined in the planning phase.

Figure 1. Gantt chart of the project. The red line identifies the date of the redaction of this report.

1. PROJECT MANAGEMENT AND ADMINISTRATION (WP1000)

Within this Work Package (i.e., WP1000), all activities related to internal project coordination and partnership management (administrative, logistical, and financial) were carried out, including the definition of the project execution plan, the kick-off meeting, and additional meeting being conducted on an almost weekly basis. These latter were instrumental for the coordinator and the partners to ensure the monitoring of project progress in relation to the defined deliverables, favoring a smooth collaboration among all the project's units. Moreover, the Sapienza University of Rome unit implemented and constantly updated a webpage for sharing the project activities.

In this regard, all dissemination activities towards the scientific community and industrial contexts were also coordinated in this WP. They include participation and organization at dedicated events. Specifically, the following contributions were written to be published in scientific journals or presented at scientific conferences:

- *Document type:* Conference paper (accepted for presentation)
Authors: M. Bortolini, E. Ferrari, M. Gamberi, F. G. Galizia, E. Giannone
Title: A Human-Digital twin model to track human motion in an experimental Cyber-Socio-Technical System
In: International Conference on Industry 4.0 and Smart Manufacturing (ISM 2024), Prague, November 20 - 22, 2024

Topic: The goal of the paper is to define a methodology to build a Human-Digital twin model of an operator working inside a plant. The methodology involves the use of control volumes and motion capture technologies to give access to a flexible and customizable framework tracking the operator's movements

- *Document type:* Conference paper (accepted for presentation)
Authors: A. J. Nakhal Akel, F. Simone, E. Stefana, L. Fedele, R. Patriarca
Title: System-theoretic analysis for the identification of emerging risk in Cyber-Physical systems
In: International Conference on Industry 4.0 and Smart Manufacturing (ISM 2024), Prague, November 20 - 22, 2024
Topic: This paper explores the emerging risks in industrial settings due to energy transition, focusing on safety and security in cyber-physical systems. It highlights the need for system interconnection between humans and technologies to meet sustainability goals. The study applies System-Theoretic Process Analysis (STPA) to identify risks associated with integrating renewable energy technologies. Results reveal control flaws and unsafe interactions that could lead to accidents. A case study on the storage of dangerous substances shows how automated tank controls may be vulnerable to disruptions
- *Document type:* Journal article (under review)
Authors: G. Mazzuto, I. Pietrangeli, M. Orteni, F. E. Ciarapica, M. Bevilacqua
Title: Leveraging digital twin for operational resilience in the oil and gas industry when cyber security fails
In: International Open Access Multidisciplinary Journal Array, Elsevier
Topic: This paper presents a digital twin of an experimental plant replicating an oil and gas transportation system, addressing limitations from previous studies. The model helps managers simulate anomalous conditions and determine corrective actions to improve system resilience. It integrates components and their interdependencies, including the role of PID regulators in monitoring and correcting system errors. After evaluating various algorithms, Gradient Boosted Tree was chosen for its stability and performance. Simulated scenarios demonstrate the model's effectiveness, though further data acquisition is needed to refine it due to fluctuations caused by the air element
- *Document type:* Conference paper
Authors: I. Pietrangeli, G. Mazzuto, F. E. Ciarapica, M. Bevilacqua
Title: Artificial Intelligence and Digital twin for Effective Risk Management in an experimental plant
In: 36th European Modeling & Simulation Symposium EMSS 2024, 21st International Multidisciplinary Modeling & Simulation Multiconference, Tenerife, Spain, September 18 - 20, 2024

Topic: The Oil & Gas industry is undergoing digital transformation with the integration of Digital twins and AI, though adoption is still limited. This study demonstrates the use of AI-generated models to analyze the behavior of a vertical tank in an experimental plant, utilizing real-time data. Building on previous research, the approach incorporates two AI algorithms that predict tank pressures and water levels with high accuracy (99.98% and 99.75%). The model enhances system performance, detecting anomalies and improving plant operations. This case highlights the transformative potential of AI and Digital twins for safer, more efficient Oil & Gas plant management

- *Document type:* Conference paper

Authors: H. Alimam, G. Mazzuto, M. Ortenzi, C. Paciaroti, F. E. Ciarapica, M. Bevilacqua

Title: Emanating Intelligent Mechatronics in the Oil and Gas Industry: A Resilient Approach to Refine the Perceptive and Maturity Fusion of Pneumatically Actuated Control Valves Within the Digital Triplet Paradigm

In: 2024 IEEE International Conference on Engineering, Technology, and Innovation (ICE/ITMC), Funchal, Portugal, June 24 - 28, 2024

Topic: This paper explores the integration of automation, mechatronics, human input, and AI, focusing on enhancing the resilience of mechatronic systems. These systems, which include sensing, actuation, and decision-making capabilities, improve system intelligence. The study utilizes real-time data, predictive analytics, and prescriptive techniques to enhance digital maturity. Specifically, it examines pneumatically actuated control valves in the oil and gas industry, integrating predictive analytics and AI to create cloud-based soft sensors. The approach incorporates deep learning to predict valve behavior, advancing cognitive capabilities and insights in cyberspace

- *Document type:* Conference paper

Authors: F. Simone, A. J. Nakhal Akel, M. Lombardi, G. Di Gravio, R. Patriarca

Title: Human-Hardware in the Loop (HHIL) STAMP-based simulations to model cyber-physical complexity in experimental high-risk plants

In: European STAMP Workshop and Conference ESWC 2024, Alexandroupolis, Grece, October 2 – 4, 2024

Topic: This paper presents a systemic approach for analyzing safety in Cyber-Socio-Technical Systems (CSTS) with a focus on responses to cyberattacks. It proposes using the System-Theoretic Accident Model and Processes (STAMP) to model interactions within CSTS, particularly human-to-machine and machine-to-machine interactions, through Human-Hardware In the Loop (HHIL) simulations. The research applies this approach to an Oil and Gas industry testbed simulating oil extraction, where a human operator interacts with automated controls. The HHIL model evaluates potential loss scenarios arising from cyber vulnerabilities, and a Digital twin structure is introduced to simulate destructive scenarios. The approach provides a decision support tool to manage CSTS safety and operations, extending STPA with quantifiable impacts at different interaction levels

- *Document type:* Conference paper
Authors: A. J. Nakhal Akel, F. Simone, M. Lombardi, F. Costantino, G. Di Gravio, M. Tronci, M. Bortolini, G. Mazzuto, R. Patriarca
Title: Dealing with I5.0 complexity: cyber-socio-technical systems modelling and analysis
In: XXIX SUMMER SCHOOL “Francesco Turco” – Industrial Systems Engineering Otranto, Italy September 11-13, 2024
Topic: This paper discusses the transition from Industry 4.0 (I4.0) to Industry 5.0 (I5.0), emphasizing new challenges in industrial systems and human-machine collaboration. It introduces the concept of cyber-socio-technical systems (CSTS), which highlights the importance of integrating cyber-physical technologies, human agents, and organizational structures. The paper argues for updates in safety science to address the complexities of modern industrial environments from a CSTS perspective. Two main challenges are identified: modeling CSTS complexity and analyzing safety and resilience in CSTS applications. The paper presents methods for modeling and analyzing CSTS to promote safer, more resilient operations.

During the second year of the project, additional contributions will be prepared for submission to international scientific journals and both national and international conferences. These contributions will focus on the main topics of the project: i.e., the development and testing of Human-Hardware in the Loop (HHIL) digital twin models to assess system cyber resilience, and the identification of guidelines to manage cyber-attacks at critical industrial facilities.

2. SYSTEM DEFINITION (WP2000)

This section includes the results obtained by means of: (i) the systematic literature review to establish the theoretical foundation for the method to be chosen (WP2100); (ii) a description of the plant and its components, with a particular focus on the human operator’s activities (WP2200); (iii) the development of the STAMP model (Leveson, 2004) and conduction of the STPA analysis (WP2300), and (iv) with respect to the obtained loss scenarios, the drafting resilience metrics for the case (WP2400).

2.1. Systematic literature review

This activity had the purpose of investigating the complexity of CSTS with a particular focus on how it is modelled in literature. The project team explores the various modelling approaches used in this field, their applications, and the growing necessity for considering cybersecurity issues in modern systems. Cybersecurity, in this context, goes beyond traditional concerns of data breaches and hacking, addressing more critical threats such as potential manipulations of physical processes that

could result in tangible damage, operational disruptions, and safety risks. The growing integration of technologies within industrial systems, particularly in the age of Industry 5.0, demands a better understanding of these systems, emphasizing the importance of security and resilience. This search for modelling approaches was conducted without limiting their scope to specific industries or systems. Each approach is assessed against various variables such as modelling techniques, system types, and industry applications.

To investigate the state-of-the-art research on CSTS modelling within industrial settings, a systematic review methodology was employed, inspired by the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) framework (Moher et al., 2009). The PRISMA framework provides structured guidelines for systematic reviews, ensuring transparency and comprehensiveness throughout the research process.

The review's core objectives were outlined by establishing the research question and selection criteria for the analysis. The following elements were considered crucial for guiding the conduction of the literature review:

- *Research question and query.* This ensured that the content for analysis was specific and relevant. The following research question was defined:

“In the context of cyber-physical systems within the broader of CSTSs, how, and to which extent, do modelling techniques integrate socio-technical aspects and human-machine interactions to enhance the safety and security of interconnected industrial systems and coupled industrial processes?”

Which translated into the following search query:

“TITLE-ABS-KEY (“cyber” AND “model” AND (“socio* technical” OR “*man*machine*))”*

- *Criteria for document selection.* This included defining inclusion/exclusion criteria, search strategies, data extraction methods, and statistical analysis plans. Table 2 includes the specification of inclusion and exclusion criteria being employed.
- *Database choice.* A comprehensive search was performed across the Scopus academic databases to identify relevant documents in line with the inclusion and exclusion criteria.

From an initial query, 183 documents were retrieved that matched the search criteria. A thorough screening process led to the exclusion of 106 documents. Reasons for exclusion included the absence of empirical research in documents categorized as literature reviews (13 documents), and conference proceedings summaries (20 documents). Other exclusions were made for papers addressing unrelated

application approaches such as organizational modelling, or cognitive modelling (52 documents). Additionally, documents not written in English, or categorized as books, theses, or reports (21 documents), were excluded. Ultimately, 77 documents met the criteria for further analysis, representing 72% of the original search results.

Upon further review, 20 documents were filtered out based on inconsistencies between the title, abstract, and full-text content, or due to inaccessibility of the full text. This resulted in a final selection of 57 documents for the subsequent analysis.

Table 2. Inclusion and exclusion criteria.

<i>Criteria</i>	<i>Inclusion</i>	<i>Exclusion</i>
Language	The analysis considered the documents only written in the English language	The documents written other than English
Type of the document	Journal manuscripts and Conference proceedings	Chapters books, Technical reports, Books, Whitepapers, Academic Theses, Lectures or Notes
Scope	Publications presenting research or non-empirical work on CSTSs modelling	Publication focused on the CSTSs modelling
Document availability	Full-text available or retrievable by the resources available at any of the project partners	Documents in which the full-text is not obtained

2.2.3 Literature review findings

The selected documents revealed three primary modelling approaches that have emerged in CSTS research, specifically:

- *Resilience Engineering Modelling.* Research within this stream emphasizes the operational performance of CSTS, particularly focusing on how systems can maintain acceptable performance levels in the face of adverse conditions. This approach emphasizes the system's ability to withstand, adapt, and recover from unexpected events, highlighting the importance of resilience in complex industrial environments. The central point of this modelling approach is the evaluation of how tasks performed by agents interact and influence each other.
- *Control Theory Modelling.* Control theory-inspired models are commonly used in CSTS research, focusing on how agents within the system make decisions that impact on the operations of others. These models offer a systemic representation of the interactions among system elements through control actions and feedback exchanges. This perspective aids in understanding how agents modify system behaviors based on shared data and feedback.

- *Information Flow Modelling.* Information flow modelling addresses how data is exchanged within a CSTS. This approach identifies the various process stages and characterizes the types of data that flow through the system. By modeling the exchange of information, this approach helps to capture the complexity of the system and the way in which data is accessed, processed, and utilized across different stages.

The analysis of the 57 selected papers revealed the distribution of research efforts across the three modelling approaches. (i) Control Theory Modelling represented the majority as the 54.38% (i.e., 31 documents) of the papers employed this approach; (ii) Resilience Engineering Modelling accounted for 24.56% (i.e., 14 documents) of the studies; while (iii) the remaining 21.05% (i.e., 12 documents) were related to Information Flow Modelling.

The review of current literature on CSTS modelling reveals a quite balanced distribution of research across control theory, resilience engineering, and information flow modelling approaches. While Control Theory models are the majority, Resilience Engineering and Information Flow approaches also contribute significantly. The integration of advanced technologies in industrial systems, particularly in the context of Industry 5.0, has led to new challenges in managing the complexity and safety of these systems. Traditionally, safety and risk management have focused on prevention and protection, but the increasing interconnectivity and complexity of systems necessitate a shift toward resilience and adaptability. From the analysis of literature, Control Theory models have proven particularly effective in mapping the interactions between physical, cyber, and human elements of CSTSs, aligning closely with traditional automation control paradigms. This has made Control Theory a key candidate for future project developments. Among the various modelling approaches related to Control Theory modelling, STAMP and STPA, stand out as effective tools for addressing the complexities of modern CSTSs. To this end, they were selected to model and analyze the experimental plant.

2.2. Experimental plant details

The plant analyzed in this project is an experimental facility located within the Department of Industrial Engineering and Mathematical Sciences (DIISM) at the University Politecnica delle Marche in Ancona, Italy. Built in the early 1990s, the plant was designed to simulate the artificial extraction of natural gas from a depleted well by using the pressure from an active oil well. As illustrated in Figure 2, to mitigate the high costs of installing pumps at the bottom of reservoirs with insufficient internal pressure to naturally lift oil and gas to the surface, a technique was developed that employs an ejector. The ejector operates by utilizing the high-pressure flow from the active well to create a vacuum effect, effectively extracting the gas and liquids from the depleted well, thereby optimizing the extraction process.

Figure 2: An example of the experimental plant system

Following the do-not-significant-harm (DNSH) principle (European Commission, 2021), as declared in the project proposal, the experimental plant uses water and air at room temperature in place of crude oil and natural gas. Figure 3 illustrates the current configuration, which has been adjusted and refined over time.

Figure 3: The current experimental plant configuration.

The plant replicates a typical extraction scenario in which the pressure from a high-pressure reservoir is used to create suction in a reservoir with insufficient pressure for transport. While crude oil and natural gas are the primary fluids in actual operations, the experimental setup substitutes these with water and air for safety reasons.

In industries such as oil, chemical, and nuclear, the transportation of two-phase gas-liquid mixtures through a single pipeline presents a common challenge. In the oil sector, for instance, the pressure within an oil field often falls short of what is needed to bring oil to the surface. The conventional solution involves installing pumps at both the surface and the bottom of the well. A more efficient alternative leverages a higher-pressure neighboring well. Gas-liquid ejectors, which combine two phases at different pressures and supply the necessary transport energy, offer distinct advantages. These include the absence of moving parts, simplicity, low maintenance and installation costs, and no sealing issues, making them ideal for handling hydrocarbon mixtures and corrosive, toxic, or radioactive gases.

In the experimental plant, a pump connected to an open tank draws water and delivers it to the ejector at a specified pressure through the inlet water line (Figure 3). The water pressure is regulated by a solenoid valve (AV1 in Figure 4). Inside the ejector, pressure energy is converted into kinetic energy, creating a vacuum that draws in air from the atmosphere via the inlet airline (red line in Figure 3). At the ejector outlet, the resulting two-phase mixture flows into a vertical pressure tank, which acts as a separator for the liquid and gaseous components. This occurs through the inlet mixture line (black and yellow lines in Figure 3).

Figure 4: The current experimental plant configuration with main components identification.

In this section of the plant, two additional solenoid valves (AV2 and AV3 in Figure 4) manage the flow of water and air at the outlet via the outlet water and air lines. These valves regulate both the pressure and liquid level inside the tank. Figure 4 highlights the main components of the plant, including sensors and solenoid valves, which are detailed in Table 3.

Table 3: Description of main components equipped on the plant.

<i>ID</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Unit of measure</i>	<i>Component name</i>
S1	Inlet water pressure sensor	[bar]	Endress+ Hauser Cerabar M PMP51
S2	Inlet water flow rate sensor	[m3/h]	Endress+ Hauser Promag W
S3	Ejector pressure sensor	[bar]	Setra 280°
S4	Diffuser pressure sensor	[bar]	Foxboro 841GM CII
S5	Tank pressure sensor	[bar]	Endress+ Hauser Promag W
S6	Tank water level sensor	[mm]	Foxboro IDP-10
S7	Inlet air flow rate	[m3/h]	Foxboro Vortez DN 50
S8	Outlet air flow rate	[m3/h]	Endress+ Hauser Cerabar M PMP51
AV1	Inlet water pressure valve	% of closure	Spirax Sarco 9126E
AV2	Tank water level valve	% of closure	Eckardt MB6713
AV3	Tank pressure valve	% of closure	Eckardt twin MB6713

In this context, the plant operator can perform various fundamental operations to ensure its functionality. These include starting and shutting down the system, which involve activating the pump and configuring the valves initially, or by closing the manual valves to ensure a safe shutdown. Another key activity is adjusting operating parameters, such as the water flow pressure, which can be regulated using the solenoid valve AV1, and the incoming air flow rate, which can be modified by adjusting AV3 to control the composition of the two-phase flow. Indeed AV3, controlling the tank pressure, can increase or decrease the inlet air flow rate imposing a constraint to the ejector exit. Thus, the operator can also manage the liquid level and tank pressure by using valves AV2 and AV3 to maintain the desired values.

System monitoring is essential and relies on data provided by sensors for pressure, level, and flow rate, which are crucial for verifying the proper functioning of the plant. In case of anomalies, the operator can perform diagnostics to identify potential issues or manually intervene by adjusting the valves or shutting down the system in emergencies. Routine maintenance includes cleaning the pipelines to remove any residues and periodically inspecting the valves, ejector, and sensors to ensure system efficiency. These operations require specific technical skills and a thorough understanding of the system dynamics.

2.3. STAMP model and STPA analysis

The STPA is a safety analysis method developed by Leveson (2018). It is meant to extend traditional hazard analysis techniques by focusing not only on single component failures, but also on the interactions within complex systems. On this path, STPA differs from traditional safety analysis methods, such as Fault Tree Analysis (FTA) and Failure Modes and Effects Analysis (FMEA), mainly because it looks at the system as a whole. Accordingly, the method focuses on analyzing the system's safety control structure (SCS) which highlights all the interaction between system components. STPA provides a structured approach to identify potential hazards and unsafe control actions within a system

In this report the key steps involved in performing STPA are outlined first, then it offers indication on its application to the plant described in Section 2.2.

The first step in performing STPA is to clearly define the purpose of the analysis, thus, the system to analyze and its boundaries. This includes specifying the system's losses of interest, and the hazards leading to those losses. The definition of hazards also permits us to identify the so-called system level constraints, i.e., all those situations which must verify to ensure that the hazards lead to no losses.

The loss identified for the STPA of experimental plant under analysis are reported in Table 4. An ID has been associated with each loss; such ID is used in the rest of the report to point at specific losses.

Table 4: Loss identified for the STPA.

<i>ID</i>	<i>Loss description</i>
L-01	Damage to plant equipment
L-02	Injuries (or deaths) of people working on the plant
L-03	Unavailability of the plant
L-04	Leakage of sensitive information about the plant
L-05	Damage to the laboratory's facilities (outside of the plant)
L-06	Damage to the laboratory's facilities (outside of the plant)
L-07	Loss of reputation

The hazards identified for the STPA of experimental plant under analysis are reported in Table 5. An ID has been associated with each hazard; such ID is used in the rest of the report to point at specific hazards.

Table 5: Hazards identified for the STPA.

<i>ID</i>	<i>System level hazard description</i>	<i>Link to losses</i>
H-01	The pressure of the fluid(s) exceeds the maximum acceptable limits	L-01, L-02, L-05
H-02	The pressure of the fluid(s) does not allow the movement of the fluid(s) within the plant	L-03
H-03	The quantity of the fluid(s) inside the system exceeds the maximum acceptable limits	L-01, L-02, L-05
H-04	The quantity of fluid(s) does not allow the movement of the fluid(s) within the plant	L-03
H-05	The system is unable to automatically collect data about the operations of the plant	L-03
H-06	The system shares collected data outside its infrastructure	L-04

The system level constraints identified for the experimental plant under analysis are reported in Table 6. An ID has been associated with each system level constraints; such ID is used in the rest of the report to point at specific system level constraints.

Table 6: System level constraints identified for the STPA.

<i>ID</i>	<i>System level constraint description</i>	<i>Link to hazards</i>
SC-01	If the pressure of the fluid(s) exceeds the maximum acceptable limits, the system must be able to detect its value and to restore acceptable pressure conditions	H-01
SC-02	If the pressure of the fluid(s) does not allow the movement of the fluid(s) within the plant, the system must be able to detect the gap and to increase the pressure value	H-02
SC-03	If the quantity of the fluid(s) inside the system exceeds the maximum acceptable limits, the system must be able to detect its value and to discharge the additional quantity without compromising the surrounding environment	H-03
SC-04	If the quantity of fluid(s) does not allow the movement of the fluid(s) within the plant, the system must be able to detect the gap and to increase the quantity of fluid(s) within the plant	H-04
SC-05	If the system is unable to automatically collect data about the operations of the plant, it must be able to acknowledge the limitation and to have an alternative visibility about data related to the operations of the plant	H-05
SC-06	If the system shares collected data outside its infrastructure, it must be able to prevent modifications of the operations of the plant	H-06

The second step of the STPA consists in the construction of the system's SCS. Indeed, STPA assumes that accidents occur due to unsafe control actions, so it is essential to model the system's control structure highlighting all the interactions among system elements. Accordingly, this step involves creating a control structure diagram, which illustrates the relationships between controllers and controlled processes, along with feedback loops. A controller is identified as an element of the SCS which impose a control action on another element. Similarly, a controlled process is identified as an

element which received a control action. Both controllers and controlled processes are identified as blocks in a SCS, while control actions are depicted as arrows connecting the bottom edge of a block (i.e., the controller) to the top edge of another block (i.e., the controlled process). The control actions are provided by the controller based upon a feedback it receives from the controlled process. The feedback updates the process model of the controller, and it feeds its control algorithm, ultimately leading to the generation of the control action. A feedback is depicted in the SCS through an arrow connecting the top edge of a block (i.e., the controlled process) to the bottom edge of another block (i.e., the controller). Control actions and feedback identify control loops between system elements. The SCS of the experimental plant under analysis is reported in Figure 5.

The third step of the STPA consists in the identification of the unsafe control actions (UCAs) within the control actions included in the SCS. UCAs are the key to identifying what leads to potential hazards in the system. They are actions taken by the controllers (or absence of action) that may lead to unsafe states. In this step, the system's control structure is analyzed to identify the conditions under which these unsafe actions can occur. A control action can become an UCA when it: (i) is wrongly provided; (ii) is not provided at all; (iii) is provided with wrong timing (i.e., too early, or too late); and (iv) is provided with wrong duration (i.e., too short, or too long). On this premises, every control action from the SCS has been analyzed by means of the four dimensions highlighted above. Subsequently, the resulting potential UCAs have been analyzed with the experimental plant experts (i.e., operators working on plants on a daily basis) to identify whether each potential UCA is effectively an UCA. All the potential UCA have been reported in Table 7, where the ones being identified as realistic and of interest have been underlined.

Figure 5. SCS of the experimental plant.

Table 7: UCAs identified for the STPA. Underlined text identify UCAs of interest.

Control action	UCA type			
	Provided	Not provided	Timing	Duration
Modification in valve (AV1) positioning	<p>The RevPi provides a <u>wrong modification of position for the air actuated valve (AV1) while controlling the flow of water in pipeline (pump – ejector) during steady state operations</u> [H-01, H-02, H-03, H-04]</p>	<p>The RevPi does not provide any modification in the positioning of the air actuated valve (AV1) while controlling the flow of water in pipeline (pump – ejector) during steady state operations [N/A]</p>	<p>The RevPi provides <u>too early a modification in the positioning of the air actuated valve (AV1) while controlling the flow of water in pipeline (pump – ejector) during steady state operations</u> [H-01, H-03]</p>	<p>The RevPi provides for too short the <u>modification in the positioning of the air actuated valve (AV1) while controlling the flow of water in pipeline (pump – ejector) during steady state operations</u> [H-01, H-02, H-03, H-04]</p>
			<p>The RevPi provides <u>too late a modification in the positioning of the air actuated valve (AV1) while controlling the flow of water in pipeline (pump – ejector) during steady state operations</u> [H-02, H-04]</p>	<p>The RevPi provides for too long the <u>modification in the positioning of the air actuated valve (AV1) while controlling the flow of water in pipeline (pump – ejector) during steady state operations</u> [H-01, H-02, H-03, H-04]</p>
Modification in valve (AV2) positioning	<p>The RevPi provides a <u>wrong modification of position for the air actuated valve (AV2) while controlling the water level in tank during steady state operations</u> [H-01, H-02, H-03, H-04]</p>	<p>The RevPi does not provide any <u>modification in the positioning of the air actuated valve (AV2) while controlling the water level in tank during steady state operations</u> [H-01, H-02]</p>	<p>The RevPi provides <u>too early a modification in the positioning of the air actuated valve (AV2) while controlling the water level in tank during steady state operations</u> [H-01, H-03]</p>	<p>The RevPi provides for too short the <u>modification in the positioning of the air actuated valve (AV2) while controlling the water level in tank during steady state operations</u> [H-01, H-02, H-03, H-04]</p>
			<p>The RevPi provides <u>too late a modification in the positioning of the air actuated valve (AV2) while controlling the water level in tank</u></p>	<p>The RevPi provides for too long the <u>modification in the positioning of the air actuated valve (AV2) while controlling the water level in tank</u></p>

			during steady state operations <u>[H-02, H-04]</u>	during steady state operations <u>[H-01, H-02, H-03, H-04]</u>
Modification in valve (AV3) positioning	The RevPi provides a wrong modification of position for the air actuated valve (AV3) while controlling the amount of air in tank during steady state operations <u>[H-01, H-02, H-03, H-04]</u>	The RevPi does not provide any modification in the positioning of the air actuated valve (AV3) while controlling the amount of air in tank during steady state operations <u>[H-01, H-02]</u>	The RevPi provides too early a modification in the positioning of the air actuated valve (AV3) while controlling the amount of air in tank during steady state operations <u>[H-01, H-03]</u>	The RevPi provides for too short the modification in the positioning of the air actuated valve (AV3) while controlling the amount of air in tank during steady state operations <u>[H-01, H-02, H-03, H-04]</u>
			The RevPi provides too late a modification in the positioning of the air actuated valve (AV3) while controlling the amount of air in tank during steady state operations <u>[H-02, H-04]</u>	The RevPi provides for too long the modification in the positioning of the air actuated valve (AV3) while controlling the amount of air in tank during steady state operations <u>[H-01, H-02, H-03, H-04]</u>
Change in set point water inlet pressure	The MQTT broker provides a wrong set point for water inlet pressure while sending information to the RevPi during steady state operations <u>[H-01, H-02, H-03, H-04]</u>	The MQTT broker does not provide any change in set point for water inlet pressure sending information to the RevPi during steady state operations [N/A]	The MQTT broker provides too early a change in set point for water inlet pressure sending information to the RevPi during steady state operations <u>[H-01, H-02, H-03, H-04]</u>	The MQTT broker provides for too short a change in set point for water inlet pressure sending information to the RevPi during steady state operations <u>[H-01, H-02, H-03, H-04]</u>
			The MQTT broker provides too late a change in set point for water inlet pressure sending information to the RevPi during steady state operations <u>[H-01, H-02, H-03, H-04]</u>	The MQTT broker provides for too long a change in set point for water inlet pressure sending information to the RevPi during steady state operations <u>[H-01, H-02, H-03, H-04]</u>

<p>Change in set point water pressure tank</p>	<p><u>The MQTT broker provides a wrong set point for water pressure in tank while sending information to the client during steady state operations [H-01, H-02]</u></p>	<p>The MQTT broker does not provide any change in set point for water pressure in tank while sending information to the client during steady state operations [N/A]</p>	<p>The MQTT broker provides too early a change in set point for water pressure in tank while sending information to the client during steady state operations [H-01, H-02]</p> <p><u>The MQTT broker provides too late a change in set point for water pressure in tank while sending information to the client during steady state operations [H-01, H-02]</u></p>	<p><u>The MQTT broker provides for too short a change in set point for water pressure in tank while sending information to the client during steady state operations [H-01, H-02]</u></p> <p><u>The MQTT broker provides for too long a change in set point for water pressure in tank while sending information to the client during steady state operations [H-01, H-02]</u></p>
<p>Change in set point water level tank</p>	<p><u>The MQTT broker provides a wrong set point for water level in tank while sending information to the client during steady state operations [H-01, H-02, H-03, H-04]</u></p>	<p>The MQTT broker does not provide any change in set point for water level in tank while sending information to the client during steady state operations [N/A]</p>	<p>The MQTT broker provides too early a change in set point for water level in tank while sending information to the client during steady state operations [H-01, H-02, H-03, H-04]</p> <p><u>The MQTT broker provides too late a change in set point for water level in tank while sending information to the client during steady state operations [H-01, H-02, H-03, H-04]</u></p>	<p><u>The MQTT broker provides for too short a change in set point for water level in tank while sending information to the client during steady state operations [H-01, H-02, H-03, H-04]</u></p> <p><u>The MQTT broker provides for too long a change in set point for water level in tank while sending information to the client during steady state operations [H-01, H-02, H-03, H-04]</u></p>
<p>Change in PID 1 constants</p>	<p><u>The MQTT broker provides a wrong change in PID 1 constants while sending information to the client during steady state operations [N/A]</u></p>	<p>The MQTT broker does not provide any change in PID 1 constants while sending information to the client during steady state operations [N/A]</p>	<p>The MQTT broker provides too early a change in PID 1 constants while sending information to the client during steady state operations [N/A]</p>	<p><u>The MQTT broker provides for too short a change in PID 1 constants while sending information to the client during steady state operations [N/A]</u></p>

			<u>The MQTT broker provides too late a change in PID 1 constants while sending information to the client during steady state operations [N/A]</u>	<u>The MQTT broker provides for too long a change in PID 1 constants while sending information to the client during steady state operations [N/A]</u>
Change in PID 2 constants	<u>The MQTT broker provides a wrong change in PID 2 constants while sending information to the client during steady state operations [N/A]</u>	The MQTT broker does not provide any change in PID 2 constants while sending information to the client during steady state operations [N/A]	<u>The MQTT broker provides too early a change in PID 2 constants while sending information to the client during steady state operations [N/A]</u> <u>The MQTT broker provides too late a change in PID 2 constants while sending information to the client during steady state operations [N/A]</u>	<u>The MQTT broker provides for too short a change in PID 2 constants while sending information to the client during steady state operations [N/A]</u> <u>The MQTT broker provides for too long a change in PID 2 constants while sending information to the client during steady state operations [N/A]</u>
Change in PID 3 constants	<u>The MQTT broker provides a wrong change in PID 3 constants while sending information to the client during steady state operations [N/A]</u>	The MQTT broker does not provide any change in PID 3 constants while sending information to the client during steady state operations [N/A]	<u>The MQTT broker provides too early a change in PID 3 constants while sending information to the client during steady state operations [N/A]</u> <u>The MQTT broker provides too late a change in PID 3 constants while sending information to the client during steady state operations [N/A]</u>	<u>The MQTT broker provides for too short a change in PID 3 constants while sending information to the client during steady state operations [N/A]</u> <u>The MQTT broker provides for too long a change in PID 3 constants while sending information to the client during steady state operations [N/A]</u>
Definition of set point water inlet pressure	<u>The human controller provides a wrong definition of set point for water inlet pressure while controlling</u>	The human controller does not provide any change in the definition of set point for water inlet pressure while	The human controller provides too early a change in the definition of set point for water inlet pressure while	<u>The human controller provides for too short a change in the definition of set point for water inlet</u>

	<u>the plant during steady state operations [H-01, H-02, H-03, H-04]</u>	controlling the plant during steady state operations [N/A]	controlling the plant during steady state operations [H-01, H-02, H-03, H-04]	<u>pressure while controlling the plant during steady state operations [H-01, H-02, H-03, H-04]</u>
			<u>The human controller provides too late a change in the definition of set point for water inlet pressure while controlling the plant during steady state operations [H-01, H-02, H-03, H-04]</u>	<u>The human controller provides for too long a change in the definition of set point for water inlet pressure while controlling the plant during steady state operations [H-01, H-02, H-03, H-04]</u>
Definition of set point water pressure in tank	<u>The human controller provides a wrong definition of set point for water pressure in tank while controlling the plant during steady state operations [H-01, H-02]</u>	The human controller does not provide any change in the definition of set point for water pressure in tank while controlling the plant during steady state operations [N/A]	The human controller provides too early a change in the definition of set point for water pressure in tank while controlling the plant during steady state operations [H-01, H-02]	<u>The human controller provides for too short a change in the definition of set point for water pressure in tank while controlling the plant during steady state operations [H-01, H-02]</u>
			<u>The human controller provides too late a change in the definition of set point for water pressure in tank while controlling the plant during steady state operations [H-01, H-02]</u>	<u>The human controller provides for too long a change in the definition of set point for water pressure in tank while controlling the plant during steady state operations [H-01, H-02]</u>
Definition of set point water level in tank	<u>The human controller provides a wrong definition of set point for water level in tank while controlling the plant during steady state operations</u>	The human controller does not provide any change in the definition of set point for water level in tank while controlling the plant during steady state operations	The human controller provides too early a change in the definition of set point for water level in tank while controlling the plant during steady state operations	<u>The human controller provides for too short a change in the definition of set point for water level in tank while controlling the plant</u>

	[H-03, H-04]	[N/A]	[H-03, H-04]	during steady state operations [H-03, H-04]
			The human controller provides too late a change in the definition of set point for water level in tank while controlling the plant during steady state operations [H-03, H-04]	The human controller provides for too long a change in the definition of set point for water level in tank while controlling the plant during steady state operations [H-03, H-04]
Definition of PID 1 constants (AV1)	The human controller provides a wrong definition of PID 1 constants while controlling the plant during steady state operations [N/A]	The human controller does not provide any change in definition of PID 1 constants while controlling the plant during steady state operations [N/A]	The human controller provides too early a change in definition of PID 1 constants while controlling the plant during steady state operations [N/A]	The human controller provides for too short a change in definition of PID 1 constants while controlling the plant during steady state operations [N/A]
			The human controller provides too late a change in definition of PID 1 constants while controlling the plant during steady state operations [N/A]	The human controller provides for too long a change in definition of PID 1 constants while controlling the plant during steady state operations [N/A]
Definition of PID 2 constants (AV2)	The human controller provides a wrong definition of PID 2 constants while controlling the plant during steady state operations [N/A]	The human controller does not provide any change in definition of PID 2 constants while controlling the plant during steady state operations [N/A]	The human controller provides too early a change in definition of PID 2 constants while controlling the plant during steady state operations [N/A]	The human controller provides for too short a change in definition of PID 2 constants while controlling the plant during steady state operations [N/A]
			The human controller provides too late a change in definition of PID 2 constants while	The human controller provides for too long a change in definition

			<u>controlling the plant during steady state operations [N/A]</u>	<u>of PID 2 constants while controlling the plant during steady state operations [N/A]</u>
Definition of PID 3 constants (AV3)	<u>The human controller provides a wrong definition of PID 3 constants while controlling the plant during steady state operations [N/A]</u>	The human controller does not provide any change in definition of PID 3 constants while controlling the plant during steady state operations [N/A]	The human controller provides too early a change in definition of PID 3 constants while controlling the plant during steady state operations [N/A]	<u>The human controller provides for too short a change in definition of PID 3 constants while controlling the plant during steady state operations [N/A]</u>
			<u>The human controller provides too late a change in definition of PID 3 constants while controlling the plant during steady state operations [N/A]</u>	<u>The human controller provides for too long a change in definition of PID 3 constants while controlling the plant during steady state operations [N/A]</u>

The last step of STPA involves the identification of causal loss scenarios, i.e., those situations which prompt the occurrence of UCAs and consequently lead to a loss or a set of them. These situations could be caused by two occurrences. A UCA could verify because of (i) inadequate feedback arriving to the controller, or (ii) an inadequate control action arriving to the controller. While control actions become inadequate when they are UCA, a slightly different reasoning shall be made regarding feedback. Indeed, feedback could be inadequate if: (i) it is wrongly provided; (ii) it is missing; or (iii) it is provided with delay. On this path, it was identified the set of feedback which could lead to a UCA. For the plant under analysis, they come from sensors S1, S5, and S6. Their feedback loops are specified below:

- S1 – “Measure of input water pressure” becomes “Measured input water pressure” becomes “Input water pressure value” becomes “Indicator for input water pressure”;
- S5 – “Measure of water pressure in tank” becomes “Measured water pressure in tank” “Water pressure in tank value” becomes “Indicator for water pressure in tank”;
- S6 – “Measure of water level in tank” becomes “Measured water level in tank” becomes “Water level in tank value” becomes “Indicator for water level in tank”.

Additionally, only the human controller has indicators on the dashboard which complete the feedback provided to them, specifically: “Indicator for set point water inlet pressure”, “Indicator for set point water pressure in tank”, “Indicator for set point water level in tank”, “Indicators for PID 1 constants”, “Indicators for PID 2 constants”, “Indicators for PID 3 constants”. This feedback is the one which shall be included in the identification of the causal loss scenarios.

Traditionally, causal loss scenarios are evaluated based on the expertise of the analyst, which shall be able to relate inadequate feedback and control actions coherently and comprehensively. However, this process may lead to inaccuracies in real-world cases, where causal loss scenarios are many and some of them may be lost. To this purpose, the research team developed an automated tool to automatically identify all possible causal loss scenarios, leaving to the expert judgement their approval only. The logic of the automated tool has been included in a Python script, which functions as follows. The scripts take as input all the UCAs of interest, and the feedback and control actions entering to each controller. Then, it iterates each UCA pairing it with all the possibilities for control actions and feedback entering the controller to be inadequate. The script returns a textual output of the type:

“<UCA> because the <Feedback to the controller generating the UCA> is <Type of inadequate feedback>, and the <Control action to the controller generating the UCA> is <Type of inadequate control action>”

With elements of type <Feedback to the controller generating the UCA> and <Control action to the controller generating the UCA> equal to the number of feedback and control actions entering the controller generating the UCA under analysis. An example of output is provided below:

“The RevPi provides a wrong modification of position for the air actuated valve (AV1) while controlling the flow of water in pipeline (pump – ejector) during steady state operations because the measure of input water pressure is wrongly provided, and the measure of input air flow rate is not provided, and the measure of water pressure in tank is provided with delay”

Where the UCA “The RevPi provides a wrong modification of position for the air actuated valve (AV1) while controlling the flow of water in pipeline (pump – ejector) during steady state operations” has been evaluated with respect to three feedback arriving to the controller.

The automation of this step lead to the identification of numerous causal loss scenarios, which provided a basis for the definition of simulation scenarios to be tested on the HHIL digital twin.

2.4. Draft resilience metrics

After the conduction of the STPA, the report D2000C was drafted to review scientific literature highlighting (i) approaches for resilience and cyber resilience measurement, and (ii) strategies of cyber-physical attacks. The purpose of this activity was to connect the output of the STPA with existing cyber-attack strategies, ultimately leading to the definition of potential scenarios to simulate. The report aimed at proposing draft resilience metrics for possible cyber-physical attack scenarios in the testbed used in the RESIST project. The approach of comparing baseline performance with the disrupted one is the one that will be adopted. The specificity of performance profiles will be defined once the experimental testbed is completed, and both the human and hardware digital twin will be merged in HHIL. Indeed, specific simulation scenarios have to be defined as they affect the data collection process employed.

With respect to the SCS developed during STPA, the feedback and control actions can be used to depict the current state of functioning of the plant. Nevertheless, feedback and control actions can be targeted by cyber-physical attacks, so they are not sufficient to depict the resilient performance. To collect such measures, there is the need to consider both information coming from plant functioning and operator's movements. Such measures should be paired with the measure of process parameters, specifically, water level in the tank and pressure in the pipelines (outputs in the SCS). Threshold values of the two measures could be defined to differentiate the criticality of the scenarios being simulated. Such thresholds, and the feedback/control actions being targeted define the simulation scenarios. Some insights into potential simulation scenarios to be tested are reported at the end of this report as they are part of WP5000.

Comparing all these measures, a result similar to the one exemplified in Figure 6 is expected. The plot in Figure 6d depicts a system performance over time. Specifically, the water level in the tank serves as an example. Such a level is measured by a sensor (cf. Figure 6c) which has been disrupted by a (e.g.,) an attack strategy which managed to mask the measure, and faked the tank to be too full (i.e., red line in Figure 6c represents a compromised measure). As a result of the feedback measure, the actuator (i.e., the valve, cf. Figure 6b) closes, and the tank starts drawing water. This results in a difference with the expected baseline performance (i.e., dashed line in Figure 6d). However, the performance is recovered because of a controller (i.e., human operator) that intervenes in the valve. Figure 6a takes as an example the distance between the human operator and the valve. They get close to the valve and re-open it, refilling the tank. The cyber resilience of such simple scenario is evaluated by (e.g.) measuring the resilience triangle highlighted in Figure 6d.

Figure 6. Example of cyber resilience measure for the testbed plant.

Overall, this reasoning serves as a baseline for drafting cyber resilience metrics for the case study of the RESIST project and guiding the definition of the cyber-physical attacks scenarios to be simulated (Simone et al., 2023). As anticipated, developing additional details about both these aspects will be the focus of the subsequent project's activities (i.e., WP5000).

3. CYBER-PHYSICAL DIGITAL TWIN DEVELOPMENT (WP3000)

This section includes a description of the activities being conducted for the development of the plant digital twin. The following subsections specify: (i) which plant components were decided to be modelled in the digital twin (WP3100); (ii) how the digital twin works and how it was tested and validated, including some exemplary simulation outputs (WP3200); and (iii) how the physical plant relates with the human operator's activities and how such interactions are managed in the digital twin (WP3300).

3.1. Modelled plant components

The pump-ejector system, the closed tank, and the PID controllers are crucial components in the operation of the plant, and their proper functioning is essential for ensuring safe and optimized performance. In the context of the digital twin, modeling these components allows for accurate real-time simulations, providing valuable insights into the interactions between various system elements. The pump-ejector system plays a key role in fluid transportation, while the closed tank serves as a separation and storage element, vital for maintaining process stability. PID controllers are essential for monitoring and controlling pressure and levels within the plant, correcting prediction errors, and ensuring the achievement of desired operational conditions. Their integration into the digital twin enables a faithful replication of the plant's real dynamics, offering a valuable tool for enhancing system management and maintenance.

3.1.1. Pump-ejector system

The pump-ejector model highlights the interdependence between the water pump and the ejector. The pump operates at maximum pressure and flow rate, but the actuated valve allows modulation of these variables. The ejector uses high-pressure water to create a low-pressure zone, drawing in air and mixing the two fluids (Koirala et al., 2021). The pressure at the pump inlet is influenced by the internal tank pressure and water level, as the ejector sits between the pump and the tank. This relationship leads to a model for predicting inlet water pressure, which depends on valve closure, tank pressure, and water level.

Bernoulli's and continuity equations (Arakeri, 2000; Hansen, 2023) describe the connection between water pressure and flow rate, though factors like pipe roughness, corrosion, and fluid viscosity complicate the direct application of traditional physical laws. Therefore, an additional model is used to define this relationship. The air flow rate aspirated by the ejector depends on water pressure and tank pressure, expressed through a mathematical model.

These considerations, along with the general model structure, explain the pump-ejector system. The simulation steps include predicting the inlet water pressure and adjusting the valve closure based on the PID controller, while the flow rates are calculated based on the pressures within the system (Pietrangeli et al., 2023).

3.1.2. Closed vertical tank

The closed vertical tank is a complex system where air and water enter through the inlet, influencing various internal variables. The mixture increases both the water and air volume inside the tank, directly affecting the water level and internal pressure. The total inlet flow rate is the sum of the flow rates of air and water. The water level depends on both the inlet and outlet water flow rates, as shown in the model, with the outlet flow rate being controlled by a PID valve located at the bottom of the

tank. Since the outlet flow is unmeasured, it is expressed as a function of the water level, PID setpoint, and other parameters.

The water inlet flow rate is influenced by the ejector's behavior, which depends on system pressures and flows. This relationship is modeled as a function of the internal tank pressure and the inlet air flow rate. The overall water level depends on the inlet mixture flow rate, internal tank pressure, and the action of the PID-controlled outlet valve.

Similarly, the tank pressure is managed by a valve at the top, controlled by a PID that regulates the air outlet flow to maintain stable pressure. The tank pressure depends on the air volume, water level, and both the inlet and outlet air flow rates. The air outlet flow is regulated by the PID and can be expressed as a function of the pressure and setpoint.

In conclusion, the internal tank pressure depends on the inlet mixture flow, water level, and the air outlet valve control, and the tank level is modeled using these relationships. These equations form the basis for regression models of both tank pressure and level.

3.1.3. PID regulators and system criticalities

A crucial characteristic of a resilient, complex engineered system is its ability to recover from disruptions and maintain optimal performance (Yodo et al., 2018). PID controllers are key to the resilience of industrial plants, as they ensure precise control of critical process variables like pressure, flow, and level. In the considered plant, the PID controllers manage the inlet water pressure (PID1, see Figure 7), tank water level (PID2), and tank pressure (PID3), as shown in Figure 7 and Figure 8. This precise control is essential for maintaining safe, efficient operations, preventing inefficiencies or failures, and reducing wear on equipment (Alfaro & Vilanova, 2022). By stabilizing these variables, PID controllers also help minimize maintenance needs and extend the plant operational lifespan.

Figure 7: The experimental plant components involved in the control of the inlet water pressure (PID1).

Figure 8: The experimental plant components controlling the tank water level (PID2) and pressure (PID3).

PID controllers safeguard the plant's integrity by preventing hazardous conditions that could cause damage or compromise safety. They also provide redundancy, ensuring that if one controller fails, others can take over, thereby maintaining process control and enhancing the system's overall resilience (Borase et al., 2021). A digital twin can improve plant resilience assessment and maintenance, especially in the context of cyber-attacks. By simulating potential attacks, the digital twin helps assess their impact and identify vulnerabilities, allowing for the development of effective mitigation strategies.

The digital twin also supports continuous monitoring of PID performance, detecting anomalies early and enabling rapid responses to incidents. It allows for optimization of PID parameters to improve plant stability and performance and facilitates testing new configurations and control strategies

without disrupting operations (Qamsane et al., 2022). Additionally, the digital twin is valuable for staff training, simulating emergencies to improve preparedness. It enhances system security by integrating simulation data, updating control software, and restricting remote access, reducing risks and improving safety. The digital twin also contributes to continuity planning, ensuring plant operation even during cyber-attacks.

The overall structure of the digital twin under study includes models of the ejector and vertical tank, which influence each other, as shown in Figure 9. However, the three PID controllers will not be modelled, as the current settings of the actual plant, as shown in the table, will be used for comparison with the digital twin controllers.

Figure 9: The digital twin architecture

The three PID controllers will not be modelled, as the current settings applied to the actual plant will be used, as reported in Table 8.

Table 8: The PID controller parameters applied on the experimental plant.

Inlet water pressure PID1		Tank water level PID2		Tank pressure PID3	
Kp	0.8	Kp	1.7	Kp	1
Kd	0	Kd	0.1	Kd	0
Ki	0.4	Ki	0.7	Ki	0.7

3.2. Experimental campaign to model the digital twin

To model the various components involved in the system, a series of tests were conducted on the experimental plant under safe conditions, as detailed in Table 9. These tests aimed to better understand the behavior of the system as key variables changed (Pietrangeli et al., 2024). The acquired data from these tests includes several important variables. The first three columns represent the setpoints of the three PID controllers (SP_AV1, SP_AV2, and SP_AV3). Following these, the sensor readings (S1 to S8) and the percentage of closure for the valves AV1, AV2, and AV3 are recorded. The "ONoff" variables (ONoff1, ONoff2, ONoff3) indicate whether the corresponding PID controllers are active.

The table includes the test index (ID) and the specific setpoints for water pressure, tank water level, and internal tank pressure (SPV1 [bar], SPV2 [mm], SPV3 [bar]) for each PID controller. In some tests, the PID controllers were turned off (denoted as "Pid off"). Additional columns indicate the number of samples collected and the duration of each test in seconds. These tests provided valuable data for constructing accurate models of system behavior.

Table 9: Tests developed for the study.

<i>ID</i>	<i>SP_V1 [bar]</i>	<i>SP_V2 [mm]</i>	<i>SP_V3 [bar]</i>	<i>Samples</i>	<i>Duration [sec]</i>
0	Pid off	Pid off	Pid off	2104	210.4
1	Pid off	Pid off	1.3	2100	210
2	Pid off	Pid off	1.5	2108	210.8
3	Pid off	Pid off	2	1785	178.5
4	Pid off	299.982	Pid off	2102	210.2
5	Pid off	450.013	Pid off	2410	241
6	Pid off	600	Pid off	2292	229.2
7	4.5	Pid off	Pid off	2487	248.7
8	5.5	Pid off	Pid off	2409	240.9
9	5.5	299.982	1.3	2018	201.8
10	4.5	299.982	1.3	2432	243.2
11	5.5	299.982	1.5	2125	212.5
12	4.5	299.982	1.5	2423	242.3
13	4.5	299.982	2	2411	241.1

14	4.5	450.013	1.5	2417	241.7
15	4.5	450.013	1.5	2417	241.7
16	4.5	450.013	2	2419	241.9
17	4.5	600	1.3	2710	271
18	4.5	600	1.5	2960	296
19	4.5	600	2	1284	128.4
20	Pid off	299.982	1.3	2590	259
21	Pid off	299.982	1.5	2422	242.2
22	5.5	299.982	2	2980	298
23	Pid off	299.982	2	2759	275.9
24	Pid off	450.013	1.3	2619	261.9
25	Pid off	450.013	1.5	2750	275
26	Pid off	450.013	2	2644	264.4
27	Pid off	600	1.3	3341	334.1
28	Pid off	600	1.5	2766	276.6
29	Pid off	600	2	3047	304.7
30	5.5	450.013	1.3	2160	216
31	5.5	450.013	1.5	3066	306.6
32	5.5	450.013	2	3411	341.1
33	5.5	600	1.3	2618	261.8
34	5.5	600	1.5	2141	214.1
35	5.5	600	2	1683	168.3

During these trials, the system was configured to test various combinations of setpoints in order to analyze their impact on system behavior. Test 9 defines the standard operating condition, with an inlet water pressure of 5.5 bar, an internal tank pressure of 1.3 bar, and a water level of 300 mm. All other tests were conducted under critical conditions, deviating from the standard range to explore how the system responds to slight alterations or extreme scenarios. These deviations provide valuable insights into the system's robustness and its limits under non-standard operating conditions.

For modelling the inlet water pressure, the Gradient Boosted Tree (GBT) algorithm outperforms others with the best performance, achieving an RMSE of 0.086 and a correlation coefficient of 0.997.

In contrast, the Support Vector Machine (SVM) algorithm, while showing a similar high correlation (0.99), has significantly longer computation time (202 seconds). Neural Networks (NNs), although they also show a high correlation, have a higher mean square error compared to GBT. Results are shown in Table 10.

Table 10: Comparison of the regression algorithms. The underlined text identify best solution.

Variable	Linear Regression	Neural Network	Decision Tree	Random Forest	<u>Gradient Boosted Tree</u>	Support Vector Machine
Inlet water pressure						
Time [sec]	3	17	2	9	<u>38</u>	202
RMSE [bar]	0.988(±0.006)	0.211(±0.003)	0.11(±0.002)	0.149(±0.001)	<u>0.086(±0.006)</u>	0.157(±0.007)
COR	0.458(±0)	0.983(±0.001)	0.995(±0)	0.992(±0)	<u>0.997(±0)</u>	0.99(±0.001)
Inlet water flow rate						
Time [sec]	0.219	12	0.319	3	<u>21</u>	220
RMSE [m3/h]	0.513 (0.003)	0.163 (0.007)	0.164 (0.005)	0.166 (0.007)	<u>0.172 (0.008)</u>	0.186 (0.017)
COR	0.947 (0.0)	0.995 (0.0)	0.995 (0.0)	0.994 (0.001)	<u>0.994 (0.001)</u>	0.993 (0.001)
Inlet air flow rate						
Time [sec]	0.234	16	0.278	4	<u>23</u>	113
RMSE [m3/h]	6.109 (0.011)	2.857 (0.011)	2.991 (0.019)	2.682 (0.028)	<u>2.03 (0.08)</u>	2.676 (0.138)
COR	0.917 (0.0)	0.983 (0.0)	0.981 (0.0)	0.984 (0.0)	<u>0.991 (0.001)</u>	0.985 (0.002)
Tank level						
Time [sec]	4	25	4	58	<u>55</u>	204
RMSE [mm]	119.855 (0.030)	84.22 (0.067)	83.882 (0.076)	89.427 (0.148)	<u>44.626 (0.315)</u>	66.876 (1.763)
COR	0.419 (0.001)	0.771 (0.000)	0.772 (0.000)	0.806 (0.001)	<u>0.942 (0.001)</u>	0.866 (0.007)
Tank pressure						
Time [sec]	0.368	9	0.458	8	<u>39</u>	198
RMSE [bar]	0.003 (0.0)	0.002 (0.0)	0.001 (0.0)	0.013 (0.0)	<u>0.001 (0.0)</u>	0.002 (0.0)
COR	1 (0.0)	1 (0.0)	1 (0.0)	0.99 (0.0)	<u>1 (0.0)</u>	1 (0.0)

In terms of modelling the incoming water flow, NN and decision tree algorithms achieve a better correlation coefficient of 0.995, with RMSE values of 0.163 and 0.164. SVM, however, continues to

have the highest RMSE and computation time. GBT, while having a slightly higher RMSE (0.172), remains one of the top models in performance.

For predicting the inlet air flow rate, GBT performs the best, achieving the lowest RMSE (2.03) and the highest correlation (0.991). NN, decision trees, and random forests also show good performance, but GBT maintains the best balance between accuracy and error reduction, highlighting its robustness.

The tank level prediction model proves challenging for most algorithms due to higher RMSE values. GBT significantly reduces the error (RMSE = 44.626) and achieves the highest correlation (0.942), outperforming linear regression (RMSE = 119.855, COR = 0.419). SVM and Random Forest (RF) show intermediate performance.

For the tank pressure model, almost all algorithms perform well, with RMSE values near zero and high correlation coefficients. GBT and decision tree methods show ideal performance, while RF and SVM have slightly higher RMSE but still provide high correlation coefficients of 0.99 or higher.

Overall, GBT proves to be the most consistent and accurate algorithm, with low error rates across various models, making it the recommended choice for modelling plant system variables. Linear regression tends to perform poorly, particularly in more complex models like tank level and inlet air flow, while SVM shows inconsistent accuracy and much higher computation times.

After identifying GBT as the most efficient approach, hyperparameter optimization and 5-fold cross-validation were conducted. This process involved splitting the training and test datasets based on benchmark tests, ensuring data from an entire test set was included in either the training or test set, preventing information leakage between the two sets.

In most cases (see Table 11), the inlet water flow rate model performs well; however, it can be challenging in certain situations, especially when operating conditions deviate from expectations. R^2 values are generally high, with a peak of 0.984 observed in test 23, indicating that the model explains nearly all the variability in the incoming water flow. However, in test 19, a significant drop in performance is noted, with an R^2 of 0.459, indicating a marked reduction in the model's predictive ability. This suggests that the model struggles to capture the relationship between the input variables and water flow under extreme or unusual conditions. Despite these challenges, the model's overall performance remains satisfactory, as most tests yield low RMSE and high R^2 values, demonstrating its ability to predict water flow accurately under normal conditions.

Table 11: Evaluation results for the tests available.

IDx	Inlet water pressure		Inlet water flow rate		Inlet air flow rate		Tank level		Tank pressure	
	RMSE	R^2 (pval)	RMSE	R^2 (pval)	RMSE	R^2 (pval)	RMSE	R^2 (pval)	RMSE	R^2 (pval)
0	0.128	0.991 (0)	0.363	0.98 (0)	1.042	0.98 (0)	8.347	0.918 (0)	0.007	0.824 (0)
1	0.111	0.994 (0)	0.388	0.974 (0)	2.244	0.974 (0)	1.328	0.992 (0)	0.079	0.937 (0)

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2	0.092	0.996 (0)	0.368	0.978 (0)	1.772	0.978 (0)	1.291	0.994 (0)	0.079	0.95 (0)
3	0.139	0.991 (0)	0.678	0.937 (0)	1.504	0.937 (0)	0.592	0.997 (0)	0.021	0.98 (0)
4	0.119	0.989 (0)	0.425	0.968 (0)	2.247	0.968 (0)	33.806	0.701 (0)	0.007	0.86 (0)
5	0.115	0.99 (0)	0.409	0.971 (0)	2.208	0.971 (0)	22.85	0.96 (0)	0.008	0.886 (0)
6	0.117	0.99 (0)	0.304	0.983 (0)	2.011	0.983 (0)	40.599	0.978 (0)	0.007	0.901 (0)
7	0.214	0.865 (0)	0.331	0.944 (0)	3.419	0.944 (0)	3.889	0.828 (0)	0.005	0.619 (0)
8	0.188	0.96 (0)	0.376	0.962 (0)	2.053	0.962 (0)	4.241	0.875 (0)	0.005	0.819 (0)
9	0.127	0.983 (0)	0.401	0.963 (0)	3.072	0.963 (0)	7.126	0.956 (0)	0.026	0.934 (0)
10	0.192	0.942 (0)	0.397	0.943 (0)	5.131	0.943 (0)	7.521	0.941 (0)	0.017	0.963 (0)
11	0.241	0.944 (0)	0.426	0.959 (0)	3.82	0.959 (0)	6.05	0.968 (0)	0.025	0.974 (0)
12	0.386	0.748 (0)	0.535	0.897 (0)	4.938	0.897 (0)	7.351	0.947 (0)	0.015	0.989 (0)
13	0.392	0.746 (0)	0.549	0.903 (0)	4.743	0.903 (0)	6.899	0.951 (0)	0.039	0.983 (0)
14	0.398	0.766 (0)	0.594	0.89 (0)	6.389	0.89 (0)	6.215	0.995 (0)	0.021	0.982 (0)
15	0.398	0.766 (0)	0.594	0.89 (0)	6.389	0.89 (0)	6.215	0.995 (0)	0.021	0.982 (0)
16	0.39	0.776 (0)	0.577	0.901 (0)	5.156	0.901 (0)	5.136	0.997 (0)	0.018	0.997 (0)
17	0.186	0.954 (0)	0.494	0.93 (0)	4.879	0.93 (0)	7.171	0.998 (0)	0.051	0.727 (0)
18	0.356	0.781 (0)	0.599	0.86 (0)	5.62	0.86 (0)	13.616	0.992 (0)	0.019	0.985 (0)
19	1.214	0.431 (0)	2.502	0.459 (0)	15.476	0.459 (0)	30.728	0.97 (0)	0.046	0.983 (0)
20	0.102	0.992 (0)	0.361	0.975 (0)	2.385	0.975 (0)	4.542	0.978 (0)	0.032	0.89 (0)
21	0.114	0.99 (0)	0.371	0.973 (0)	2.36	0.973 (0)	4.638	0.98 (0)	0.016	0.99 (0)
22	0.203	0.944 (0)	0.429	0.94 (0)	4.61	0.94 (0)	8.075	0.927 (0)	0.122	0.948 (0)
23	0.107	0.991 (0)	0.3	0.984 (0)	2.905	0.984 (0)	4.916	0.975 (0)	0.119	0.961 (0)
24	0.105	0.992 (0)	0.364	0.974 (0)	2.43	0.974 (0)	4.326	0.998 (0)	0.032	0.913 (0)
25	0.092	0.992 (0)	0.325	0.981 (0)	1.61	0.981 (0)	14.183	0.973 (0)	0.042	0.955 (0)
26	0.173	0.973 (0)	0.399	0.963 (0)	2.2	0.963 (0)	10.99	0.984 (0)	0.015	0.999 (0)
27	0.14	0.977 (0)	0.317	0.974 (0)	2.483	0.974 (0)	10.226	0.995 (0)	0.031	0.89 (0)
28	0.133	0.988 (0)	0.471	0.954 (0)	2.765	0.954 (0)	11.599	0.995 (0)	0.03	0.967 (0)
29	0.173	0.965 (0)	0.356	0.966 (0)	6.213	0.966 (0)	20.031	0.982 (0)	0.294	0.94 (0)
30	0.236	0.94 (0)	0.423	0.953 (0)	3.529	0.953 (0)	8.284	0.993 (0)	0.033	0.922 (0)

31	0.201	0.952 (0)	0.357	0.964 (0)	2.852	0.964 (0)	6.164	0.994 (0)	0.017	0.988 (0)
32	0.191	0.959 (0)	0.405	0.96 (0)	3.32	0.96 (0)	7.213	0.992 (0)	0.025	0.998 (0)
33	0.211	0.966 (0)	0.588	0.938 (0)	3.494	0.938 (0)	8.21	0.998 (0)	0.023	0.959 (0)
34	0.253	0.95 (0)	0.573	0.95 (0)	4.291	0.95 (0)	10.945	0.996 (0)	0.035	0.964 (0)
35	0.547	0.821 (0)	0.814	0.891 (0)	15.519	0.891 (0)	22.524	0.986 (0)	0.066	0.976 (0)

Test 3 demonstrates the best model performance. For inlet water pressure, the RMSE is low at 0.139 and the R^2 is 0.991 (Figure 10), indicating a strong alignment between predictions and actual values. Similarly, the inlet water flow rate and inlet air flow rate models show good results, with RMSE values of 0.678 and 1.504, and R^2 values around 0.937, confirming accurate modelling of these parameters.

The tank level model performs exceptionally well, with an RMSE of 0.592 and an R^2 of 0.997 (see Figure), reflecting precise predictions with minimal error. The tank pressure model also delivers near-perfect results, with an RMSE of 0.021 and an R^2 of 0.980, showcasing the model's strong predictive capabilities in this test case.

Overall, the low RMSE and high R^2 values across all parameters in test 3 suggest that the system was operating under conditions well-understood and easily modelled by the algorithms, resulting in the best performance.

Figure 10: Test 3 considering the inlet water pressure prediction.

Figure 11: Test 3 considering the tank level prediction.

3.3. The plant digital twin and operator's action

Given the possible actions an operator can take on the plant, the models incorporate variables such as PIDoff, PlantOff, and VM2open, which reflect specific operational conditions influenced by the operator's decisions. For instance, the variable PIDoff indicates when the PID controllers are deactivated, while PlantOff represents the state of the entire plant when it is shut down. VM2open refers to the status of the valve in the system, specifically whether it is open or closed.

During simulation, these variables can be adjusted as a direct consequence of one or more actions taken by the operator. For example, if the operator decides to deactivate a PID controller to address an issue, the PIDoff variable would be triggered, impacting the model's prediction of system behavior. Similarly, if the operator shuts down the plant (PlantOff), the model accounts for this change, affecting all related variables and outputs. Likewise, if the operator opens or closes a valve (VM2open), this action will directly influence the fluid dynamics within the system, altering the model's calculations accordingly. An example is shown in Figure 12.

These modifications reflect real-time operator interventions, ensuring that the digital twin model accurately represents how the system behaves under changing conditions, thus providing valuable insights for decision-making and system optimization.

Figure 12: Effect of securing the system by turning off the PIDs and then the system on the inlet water pressure.

4. HUMAN DIGITAL TWIN DEVELOPMENT (WP4000)

The development of the human digital twin is carried out using the Motion Capture Perception Neuron Studio technology. This technology employs inertial sensors for data acquisition, and its reliability is demonstrated by several studies (Sers et al., 2020; Shuai et al., 2022). Inertial Motion Capture is the most widely used technology across all industry sectors, and it is also among the most accurate (Berti et al., 2023; Menolotto et al., 2020).

The selected Motion Capture technology software (Axis Studio) records the position of each of the 17 sensors (one for each major body joint) over the time (capturing at 90 fps, with the possibility of increasing up to 240 fps), as shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Axis Studio settings screen.

The output of the recording is an FBX file, which is then converted into TRC format to ease its import into Microsoft Excel for easier reading.

It is essential to assign meaning to the operator's position over time. For this reason, the concept of Control Volumes (CVs) is used. A CV is a portion of space of any size or shape, displaced wherever inside the plant, typically paired to a crucial area/equipment. Thus, to determine when the operator is working in a specific area or on a particular equipment, a presence condition within the CV is defined, i.e., when the position of certain sensors is within the limits of the CV. For this acquisition campaign, only parallelepiped-shaped CVs were used and the condition for the operator's presence is that both feet and the pelvis are inside the CV. Figure 14 shows an example of control volumes definition: on the first row it is represented the name of the CV, rows two to four contain respectively the x,y and z origin coordinates. From row five to seven the spatial dimension on each direction (respectively x,y and z) is shown, and the last row will contain the total time spent on the CV.

	A	B	C
1	Control Room	Control Panel	Water Reservoir
2	-2600	6950	-5520
3	0	0	0
4	-400	3200	0
5	3000	900	2710
6	1500	1500	1500
7	3920	1000	2020
8	0	0	0

Figure 14: Control Volumes definition.

Thanks to the acquired data and the CVs definition and usage, it is possible to extract some data regarding the operator's behavior and performance while working on the plant. To reach this goal, a MATLAB script was developed, using the xlsx dataset file containing the Motion Capture data and the number, position and dimensions of the CVs.

The script checks if the xyz coordinates of each of the body joints elected for the verification condition (feet and pelvis) are included inside each CV limits. At the same time, the distance between the operator's pelvis and the barycenter of each CV is computed. This task is repeated for every frame of the recording. For each frame that fits the verification condition, the active time of the operator on the CV is increased. The schematic of this logic is represented in Figure 15.

Figure 15: MATLAB script flowchart.

The main outputs of the MATLAB script are: plot of the distance between the operator and each CV over time; total time spent on each CV by the operator during the motion capture take; sequence of the visited CVs and time spent on each visit; operator's presence in a determined CV over time. In Figure 16 each column represents a different CV (except for the last). If the operator is working on that CV a 1 digit is shown. The last column indicates the total time spent on the CV during that visit (value expressed in seconds). The presence of 0 digits in a row means that the operator is outside of every CV.

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
1.0000	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.2916
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	23.9948
1.0000	0	0	0	0	0	0	13.7498
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	53.8534
0	0	1.0000	0	0	0	0	2.0557
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2.1568
0	0	0	0	0	1.0000	0	0.4044
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.7077
0	0	0	0	0	0	1.0000	0.3033
0	0	0	0	0	0	0	6.3020

Figure 16: Operator's visit sequence, example.

Reference examples of output of the designed MATLAB script are shown in next Figures 17 and 18. Figure 17 shows the distance between the operator and the CV during the recording process. The distance is calculated between the operator's pelvis and the barycenter of the CV.

Figure 17: Operator's distance from the Control Room over time, example.

Figure 18 shows when and for how long the operator is present within a specific CV. The operator presence is represented by a binary value.

Figure 18: Operator's presence inside Control Room over time, example.

The analysis highlighted in Figures 17 and 18 represent two distinct but related outputs: to each minimum in the operator-CV distance corresponds the presence of the operator within the aforementioned CV.

To verify the quality of the recordings and, consequently, the validity of the chosen technology, test Motion Capture recordings were performed, accompanied by simultaneous video footage. By comparing the video recording with the results of the Motion Capture acquisition, it was possible to verify the synchronization of the movements captured by the sensors. Furthermore, each dataset was filtered using a Hampel filter to remove any outliers. The video quality proved to be excellent, with an average of outliers below 2% for each capture.

Following the definition of field protocols in collaboration with the other project partners, the next step in the research by University of Bologna will be the development of a fully digital human digital twin to be integrated with the plant's digital twin, enabling the simulation of scenarios in a completely digital environment. Another activity to be undertaken will be to assess the feasibility, integrability, and potential benefits of introducing Mixed Reality (MR) technologies into data acquisition campaigns. By comparing the same routines executed with and without MR, it will be possible to determine whether the introduction of this technology contributes to reducing inefficiency parameters and how this impacts the overall resilience performance.

5. CRITICALITY ASSESSMENT OF HHIL DIGITAL TWIN (WP5000)

This section include some preliminary results related to the early developments of WP5000. Specifically, the objective is to integrate the human digital twin and the plant digital twin into a HHIL digital twin. In this regard, some ideas are presented hereafter. Please note how they can change while effectively conducting the WP.

Two simulation scenarios have been selected to test the future HHIL simulation testbed. The scenarios were chosen because they ensure optimal reproduction within the plant digital twin, while permitting to leverage hardware component without really damaging the physical plant component. The two scenarios are described in the following paragraphs.

5.1. Scenario 1 - Anomalous behavior of the vertical tank level

In this critical scenario, if a hacker alters the reading of the level sensor within the vertical tank, simulating a lower level than the actual one, the PID2 controller will attempt to close the valve AV2 to reach the standard setpoint of 300 mm. Meanwhile, PID1 and PID3 continue to operate without issues. As a result, the water inlet pressure remains around 5.5 bar, and the tank pressure stays at 1.3 bar. However, the complete closure of valve AV2 leads to an increase in the water level inside the tank, which eventually rises to approximately 700 mm, as shown in Figure 19.

Figure 19: Response of tank level behavior to tampering with the relative sensor reading

In this situation, the operator notices the critical behavior of the system because, with AV2 fully closed, no water is flowing out. The operator must quickly secure the plant by deactivating the PID

controllers, shutting down the plant, and manually closing valve VM2 to prevent water from flowing back if the level has surpassed the inlet line of the two-phase mixture into the tank. This action must be taken immediately, as an excessively high level could lead to water reaching the overflow valve, causing flooding in the surrounding area.

5.2. Scenario 2 – Anomalous behavior of the vertical tank pressure

In this critical scenario, a cyber-attack modifies the pressure sensor reading inside the vertical tank, making it display a lower pressure than the actual value. As a result, the PID3 controller, which is responsible for regulating the internal tank pressure, will adjust by attempting to close valve AV2 to reach the required setpoint of 1.3 bar. The regulator continues to close AV3 until it is fully closed, under the assumption that the tank pressure is lower than it is. Meanwhile, PID1 and PID2 continue to function normally, controlling the inlet water pressure and water level without being affected by the altered sensor data.

With the water inlet pressure remaining stable at around 5.5 bar and the water level maintained at 300 mm, the complete closure of valve AV3 leads to an increase in pressure inside the tank. This pressure rise eventually reaches approximately 1.9 bar, which is significantly higher than the normal operating pressure. Since the inlet water pressure is sufficiently high to overcome the constraint imposed by the tank pressure at the ejector's outlet, water is the only fluid that enters the system. This explains why PID1 and PID2 behave normally, as their control processes are not affected by the altered pressure readings.

However, the internal tank pressure becomes so high that it prevents the creation of the necessary vacuum for air to be sucked in through the ejector. As a result, the air intake collapses to zero, and no air enters the system. The combined effect of the high-water pressure at the ejector outlet and the lack of air intake leads to strong vibrations in the mixing pipe and the expansion vessel located at the ejector's exit, as shown in Figure 20. These vibrations pose a serious risk, as they could cause physical damage to these components and potentially result in the flooding of the surrounding area due to the imbalance between the fluid phases and the system pressure dynamics.

Figure 20: Response of the inlet air flow rate to tampering with the pressure tank sensor reading

In this case, the operator becomes aware of what is happening by observing the behavior at the ejector outlet. As soon as possible, the operator must secure the system by deactivating the PID controllers, which will fully open their respective valves, restoring stable operation of the ejector. Subsequently, the operator should shut down the plant for further control actions, such as the sensor S5 calibration.

5.3. Human digital twin integration

The experimental campaign will be carried out performing up to five recordings for each scenario, tracking human operator movements within the plant. In detail, the actions of plant start up, inspection routine, anomaly detection, and actions for operational recovery will be recorded. Thanks to the captured data and the CVs definition and usage, it will be possible to extract relevant data about the operator's behavior and performance while working on the plant.

The main outputs of the MATLAB code developed from scratch for this study will include: (i) plot of the distance between the operator and each CV over time; (ii) total time spent on each CV by the operator during the motion capture take; (iii) sequence of the visited CVs and time spent on each visit.

Proved the effectiveness and applicability of the chosen Motion Capture technology, a key challenge to be addressed by the University of Bologna is the development of a fully digital human digital twin model based on basic human movements. The main issues are to create a heterogeneous, reliable, and comprehensive movement dataset that can represent the operator's position with the highest possible accuracy. Through the development of this model and its integration with the plant's digital twin, it will be possible to conduct scenario simulations in a fully digital environment. Another step further will be the exploration of Mixed Reality technology. The analysis will need to be conducted both in terms of feasibility, considering the harsh operational context in which it is to be applied, and through

a cost-benefit analysis. The expected outcomes of this analysis include an improvement over time in the operator's intervention time during anomaly detection and plant recovery phases.

6. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE ACTIVITIES

WP5000 is currently working in progress. To this end, the following activities are expected to complete the realization of the HHIL digital twin. Specifically, the cyber-physical and human digital twins have to be effectively integrated into a single platform for system monitoring and management. At this point the two digital twins have been prepared to accomplish this integration. However, the actual integration is dependent from the simulation scenarios to be tested, to properly tune digital twin's parameters and signals to capture. The information generated by the physical and digital system must be shared with the physical and digital operator, and vice versa, through the same information infrastructure. The human digital twins must access and use as its own the information generated by the cyber-physical digital twins and, the latter, must have knowledge of the state of the former to adjust, if necessary, its status. Moreover, all this information should be analyzed together, to finally assess CSTS' resilience potential (Yarveisy et al., 2020). Hypothetical situations of plant-operator working conditions will be generated on the system to evaluate the response times and performance levels, ultimately allowing adapting the previously identified metrics to finalize a set of reliable indicators for further simulation of test cases and, subsequent effectiveness assessment.

This report includes the actual developments being made from the beginning of the project until now, which are in line with the project's deadlines. Despite the project is not completed yet, some interesting results have been already obtained, highlighting the potential of the HHIL approach to assess CSTSs resilience against cyber-attack scenarios.

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